

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D5.1 STADIEM WEBSITE

Revision: v.1.0

Work package	WP5
Task	Task 5.1
Due date	30/12/2020
Submission date	21/12/2020
Deliverable lead	MARTEL
Version	1.0
Authors	Galileo Disperati (MARTEL)
Reviewers	Nikki Peeters, Mike Matton (VRT)

Grant Agreement No.: 957321
Call: H2020-ICT-2018-2020
Topic: ICT-44-2020
Type of action: IA

Abstract	This document provides the rationale behind the STADIEM website, the technical solutions adopted for its implementation and the methodology for the results assessment.
Keywords	Website, Internet, Communication & Dissemination

WWW.STADIEM.EU

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
v0.1	13/11/2020	ToC	Galileo Disperati (MARTEL)
v0.2	15/12/2020	Content editing	Galileo Disperati (MARTEL)
v0.3	16/12/2020	Content editing	Margherita Trestini (MARTEL)
v0.4	17/12/2020	Internal Review	Nikki Peeters, Mike Matton (VRT)

DISCLAIMER

The information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable are written by the "Startup Driven Innovation in European Media" (STADIEM) project's consortium under EC grant agreement 957321 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

© 2020 - 2023 STADIEM Consortium

Project co-funded by the European Commission in the H2020 Programme		
Nature of the deliverable:		OTHER
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	✓
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to STADIEM project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable D5.1 of STADIEM presents the STADIEM website. It describes the website <https://www.stadiem.eu/> created for the project and delineates the motivation behind the concept of the website, clarifying the content of sections and defining the expected impact for the project and its target audiences.

The STADIEM website is the main communication channel presented in the Project's Dissemination and Communication Plan, which focuses on communicative actions and the generation of results. Therefore, its design, management and maintenance are key activities.

The website is the main hub of STADIEM as well as the meeting place for all stakeholders and other interested parties (e.g. Media and the general public). Dissemination and communication strategies and campaigns developed online and offline will complement each other and aim to attract visitors to the website.

The web development plan hereafter is agreed upon by the STADIEM Consortium and members of WP5, and will include impact measures and indicators.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
TABLE OF CONTENTS	4
LIST OF FIGURES	5
ABBREVIATIONS	6
1 INTRODUCTION	7
2 DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES	8
3 TECHNICAL CHARACTERISTICS	9
3.1 Full responsive content website	9
3.2 Built using Wordpress CMS	10
3.3 Connection & Data exchange protected under SSL certificate	10
3.4 Images optimized and GZIP compression for better load time	11
3.5 SEO friendly site and content	11
4 PROJECT WEBSITE STRUCTURE	12
4.1 Home	12
4.2 About	15
4.3 Community	16
4.4 Get funding	17
4.5 What's new	18
4.6 Resources	20
4.7 Contact	22
5 MEASURING RESULTS	23
6 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS	25

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1: STADIEM’S HOMEPAGE ON DESKTOP AND MOBILE DEVICES.....	9
FIGURE 2: WORDPRESS CONTENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM.....	10
FIGURE 3: WEBSITE CONTENT STRUCTURE	12
FIGURE 4: HOMEPAGE AND MAIN MENU BAR.....	13
FIGURE 5: SOME OF THE HOMEPAGE AREAS (OPEN CALLS, TECHNOLOGY FOCUS, CONSORTIUM)	14
FIGURE 6: CONTACT INFO, LEGAL AND EC DISCLAIMER	14
FIGURE 7: VISION AND OBJECTIVES SECTION	15
FIGURE 8: CONSORTIUM SECTION.....	15
FIGURE 9: THE “HOW STADIEM WORKS” SECTION	16
FIGURE 10: THE CORPORATE SECTION	16
FIGURE 11: THE INVESTORS SECTION	17
FIGURE 12: THE LINKS SECTION	17
FIGURE 13: THE “GET FUNDING” (OPEN CALLS) SECTION.....	18
FIGURE 14: THE NEWS SECTION	18
FIGURE 15: THE EVENTS SECTION.....	19
FIGURE 16: THE NEWSLETTER SECTION	19
FIGURE 17: THE PRESS RELEASE SECTION.....	20
FIGURE 18: DELIVERABLES SECTION.....	20
FIGURE 19: PRESENTATIONS SECTION.....	21
FIGURE 20: PUBLICATIONS SECTION	21
FIGURE 21: PROMO MATERIALS SECTION.....	21
FIGURE 22: VIDEOS SECTION	21
FIGURE 23: CONTACT SECTION.....	22

ABBREVIATIONS

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets

1 INTRODUCTION

The STADIEM website, launched on November 12th, 2020, has been created to serve as a project content management system for the consortium and as the main communication channel for stakeholders in the project, as well as the media and the general public.

The STADIEM website was developed to provide information about the project's aims, goals, activities and results. In addition, the website aims to address Next Generation Media innovators, publicize STADIEM Open Calls and make the project published results available.

With this aim, the website provides the following content:

- General information about the project
- Description of all the member organizations of the consortium
- Information, objectives, overview on open calls participation process
- Description of events organized/attended within the scope of the project
- Press releases and other materials focused on media
- Information about the results
- Stakeholders engagement area
- Public deliverables
- Latest news
- Contact information
- Appropriate acknowledgment and reference to the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Program funding

2 DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES

The website is the central part of the digital marketing strategy that is deployed within the Communication and Dissemination Plan of the project. The combination of online and offline actions is essential to reach all target audiences and it is vital that the actions reinforce each other to have a comprehensive dissemination and communication strategy that contributes to the achievement of impact and objectives within STADIEM.

The STADIEM website has been created with specific objectives, which respond to the communication and dissemination needs of the project.

Among them, the most highlighted are the following:

- A recognizable visual identity that aligns with the innovative spirit of the STADIEM project and that is differentiating from other projects carried out so far in the sector. In this sense, dynamic elements that reinforce the main message of STADIEM have been integrated, such as a mascot character, “guiding” the visitor throughout the website.
- With the aim to create a dynamic website, content such as news and the calendar of events is periodically updated. This way, updating content also improves the ranking on Google. Likewise, this content will be shared on social networks and the project’s newsletter, which will continue to attract visitors to the website and amplify the project’s reach.
- STADIEM website is one of the main communication and dissemination channels of the project. To maximize the scope of the project, different digital marketing strategies and ways of attracting traffic have been established:
 - **SEO:** the traffic of visits to the STADIEM website shall increase progressively throughout the course of the project thanks to the implementation of strategies oriented to drive organic traffic such as proper key-phrases distribution in each webpage, relevant meta descriptions, appropriate image alt attributes and relevant internal and external cross linking.
 - **Social networks:** through the distribution of content hosted on the STADIEM website via social channels (news about the project, industry events, infographics, etc.), we aim to increase traffic and visits.
 - **Newsletter:** A tri-monthly newsletter (together with shorter newsflashes for urgent communications) is distributed between stakeholders and the general public. This includes achievements/news of the project that direct traffic to the website. Newsletters are uploaded as well in a specific section on the website.
 - **Link building:** We are creating synergies between the STADIEM website and the partners’ websites, as well as with other relevant agents of the sector (stakeholders), encouraging the exchange of links.

3 TECHNICAL CHARACTERISTICS

3.1 FULL RESPONSIVE CONTENT WEBSITE

Responsive Web Design makes STADIEM’s website look good on all devices (desktops, tablets, and phones).

Also, responsive Web Design is about using HTML and CSS to resize, hide, shrink, enlarge, or move content and make it look good on any screen. The incorporation of the state-of-the-art techniques in design also creates a quick and intuitive user experience.

FIGURE 1: STADIEM’S HOMEPAGE ON DESKTOP AND MOBILE DEVICES

FIGURE 2: WORDPRESS CONTENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

3.2 BUILT USING WORDPRESS CMS

WordPress is an online, open source website creation tool written in PHP. It's probably the easiest and most powerful blogging and website content management system (or CMS) in existence today:

- WordPress has a lot of themes that allows us to change the design of the website quickly, perfect for a 3-year project such as STADIEM.
- Plugins make it possible to extend the functionality of the WordPress site without programming. There are over 10,000 plugins available that help to add all kinds of functionalities, like social media sharing, SEO, photo slideshows, and much more.
- WordPress is easy to update. Once a document is set up, you can update it anytime you want, which is important for engagement with your visitors and for search engines.
- Google prefers WordPress sites because they are updated more frequently, and the content tends to be structured well. A WordPress site ranks very quickly compared to a static website. Google has even publicly recommended WordPress for business sites.
- WordPress is supported by a thriving, engaged community. A recent study estimates that approximately 8% of the sites on the Internet are run by WordPress.

3.3 CONNECTION & DATA EXCHANGE PROTECTED UNDER SSL CERTIFICATE

SSL stands for Secure Sockets Layer and is a global standard security technology that enables encrypted communication between a web browser and a web server. It is utilized by 1 million of online businesses and individuals to decrease the risk of sensitive information (e.g. credit card numbers, usernames, passwords, emails, etc.) from being stolen or tampered with by hackers and identity thieves. In essence, SSL allows for a private “conversation” just between the two intended parties.

To create this secure connection, an SSL certificate (also referred to as a “digital certificate”) is installed on a web server and serves two functions:

- ➡ It authenticates the identity of the website (this guarantees visitors that they are not on a bogus site).
- ➡ It encrypts the data that is being transmitted.

3.4 IMAGES OPTIMIZED AND GZIP COMPRESSION FOR BETTER LOAD TIME

Website GZIP compression makes it possible to reduce the file size of a web file (like HTML, PHP, CSS and JavaScript files) to about 30% or less of its original size before these files get sent to the browser of a user.

This compressed file is then served to the browser of the user which in turn decompresses it automatically to load the full original file in the browser again. Enabling GZIP compression is great for improving page speed because visitors will need to download much smaller web files than the original size when browsing web pages, which speeds up the download process of these files.

3.5 SEO FRIENDLY SITE AND CONTENT

At a fundamental level, an SEO-friendly site is one that allows a search engine to explore and read pages across the site. Ensuring a search engine can easily crawl and understand the content is the first step to ensuring STADIEM’s visibility in the search engine result pages.

STADIEM’s website is SEO friendly and responds to the following standards:

- ➡ **Keyword Research/Optimization:** STADIEM’s website uses keywords in the content for maximum searchability and to generate traffic through search.
- ➡ **Content Organization:** The content is organized in a logical way and considers the European guidelines of best practices. This is not only good for SEO, but also helps visitors to find other related content easily (the longer they stay on the site, the better).
- ➡ **Content Promotion:** We can increase visibility of new content by sharing it on social networks and building links to the content (both internally and from external sites).

4 PROJECT WEBSITE STRUCTURE

STADIEM's website is the main online channel to present and disseminate all the results and events within the project. It is regularly updated by MARTEL (WP5) to provide the latest news, relevant results and highlights, in coordination with the partners.

The website is carefully designed to address the stakeholders in the most effective way, and to ensure the visibility of the project to the EU, as well as target audiences, consortium, stakeholders and the general public. Online communication strategies will be aimed at reaching a large number of stakeholders and to networking/crossover with other similar projects.

STADIEM's website was designed as an interactive channel for public information and communication among partners and stakeholders. It will also be a repository for public documents, materials, and useful information related to the project. It can be continuously improved and updated, in order to maximize the results and share them with target audiences.

The structure and design of the website used during the lifetime of STADIEM might be modified to be adapted to new needs and progress within the project.

This is the STADIEM website structure:

FIGURE 3: WEBSITE CONTENT STRUCTURE

4.1 HOME

The homepage is designed to attract the attention of viewers at first sight. The graphic content is the protagonist so that the visitor immediately has an overview of the project's ambitions and the value to stakeholders. The homepage is divided into different sections, easily distinguishable by color and composition to reflect different key areas of the project (and related website inner pages) and provide initial information:

- STADIEM in a nutshell
- What is STADIEM (more detailed info)
- Call to action to join the STADIEM community (addressing stakeholders)
- Open call info (featuring an animated countdown to the upcoming open call)
- Latest news
- Newsletter subscription button
- Events
- Technology focus (brief breakdown on focus areas)
- Consortium presentation (links and testimonials from partners)
- Social media links

All inner sections of the website are listed on the top menu bar, next to the STADIEM logo, enabling quick orientation and search.

FIGURE 4: HOMEPAGE AND MAIN MENU BAR

FIGURE 5: SOME OF THE HOMEPAGE AREAS (OPEN CALLS, TECHNOLOGY FOCUS, CONSORTIUM)

Homepage and all inner sections also provide contact information, reference to the Horizon 2020 Programme, European Commission (EC) recognition, privacy and cookie policy links.

FIGURE 6: CONTACT INFO, LEGAL AND EC DISCLAIMER

4.2 ABOUT

4.2.1 Vision & objectives

This section briefly describes STADIEM’s field of interest, the area of expertise of the consortium, and gives a short breakdown of the project’s main objectives, and invites stakeholders to subscribe to the newsletter for updates.

FIGURE 7: VISION AND OBJECTIVES SECTION

4.2.2 The consortium

This section provides a brief description of the area of expertise covered by the partners taking part in the project, followed by a grid with their logos, which serve as buttons linking to their websites.

FIGURE 8: CONSORTIUM SECTION

4.2.3 How STADIEM works

This section offers an overview on STADIEM's envisioned incubation and acceleration framework: illustrating how the various “actors” involved will interact. This is delivered through a short text, followed by simple infographics.

FIGURE 9: THE “HOW STADIEM WORKS” SECTION

4.3 COMMUNITY

4.3.1 Corporate

This section provides information specifically targeted to stakeholders belonging to the corporate realm. A brief description provides an overview on the advantages and opportunities offered by a participation to STADIEM project. A button links to the project’s contact email address, inviting visitors to get in touch.

FIGURE 10: THE CORPORATE SECTION

4.3.2 Investors

This section provides information specifically targeted to stakeholders belonging to the investors realm. A brief description provides an overview on the advantages and opportunities offered by a participation in STADIEM project. A button links to the project's contact email address, inviting visitors to get in touch.

FIGURE 11: THE INVESTORS SECTION

4.3.3 Links

This section provides links to all initiatives linked to STADIEM's focus areas and fields of interest, as well as projects sharing similar aims.

FIGURE 12: THE LINKS SECTION

4.4 GET FUNDING

This is the section dedicated to information related to STADIEM's open calls: it features a brief description of the groups to whom the calls will be addressed, as well as a statement on the type of funding that will be provided.

The section also lists the date of the first planned open call and details the envisioned four phases in the open call process, through simple graphic representations and additional descriptions. The visitors are invited to stay tuned for further updates, through a conveniently placed field for newsletter subscription (accompanied by a disclaimer regarding legal/data privacy issues).

FIGURE 13: THE “GET FUNDING” (OPEN CALLS) SECTION

4.5 WHAT’S NEW

4.5.1 Latest news

This section displays all news on progress and results of the project, as well as event participation. A regular update of this page will ensure interesting content for the STADIEM community, which will be shared on the related dissemination and communication channels of the project (social networks Twitter and LinkedIn) to attract visits and achieve a high ranking on Google.

FIGURE 14: THE NEWS SECTION

4.5.2 Events

This page is dedicated to conferences, expos, symposiums and workshops in which STADIEM takes part or that are organized within the project. It presents the information in a calendar-type layout, linking to individual pages that contain dates, venues, topic areas, and practical information for each event.

FIGURE 15: THE EVENTS SECTION

4.5.3 Newsletter

This page features a field for newsletter subscription (accompanied by a disclaimer regarding legal/data privacy issues). All newsletters issued over the course of the project will be also featured on this page.

FIGURE 16: THE NEWSLETTER SECTION

4.5.4 Press releases

This section collects all press releases issued by STADIEM's partners over the course of the project. The links to a downloadable PDF version of each press release are available on this page.

FIGURE 17: THE PRESS RELEASE SECTION

4.6 RESOURCES

This section is dedicated to all resources and materials that disseminate STADIEM's results.

The content is organized into five sub-sections for different types of items:

- Public deliverables (containing the list of all expected public deliverables for the project, which will be updated with links to downloadable PDFs post-submission)
- Presentations (with downloadable PDFs or links to videos of presentations held during events)
- Publications (which will be updated with downloadable PDFs of scientific publications issued during the project, or external links to them)
- Promo materials (which will be updated with items such as flyers, posters, brochures, etc. produced during the project)
- Videos (featuring embedded videos produced over the course of the project)

No.	Deliverable	Month
DE1	Community Building Strategy	03
...		
DE3	Community map and database	06
DE4		20
		36
DE5		12
DE6	Community building activity report	24
DE7		36
DE3	A comprehensive startup/incubation framework and toolkit for the European media sector startup industry	15
DE4		35
DE1	Open call documents KIT and third-party financing rules	04
DE2		15
DE5		09
DE6	Analytics on the submitted proposals	20

FIGURE 18: DELIVERABLES SECTION

FIGURE 19: PRESENTATIONS SECTION

FIGURE 20: PUBLICATIONS SECTION

FIGURE 21: PROMO MATERIALS SECTION

FIGURE 22: VIDEOS SECTION

4.7 CONTACT

This section provides an email form to contact STADIEM. This enables stakeholders, other projects interested in networking and the general public, to be able to get in touch with the project.

The screenshot shows the 'CONTACT' page of the STADIEM website. The page has a dark purple header with the 'STADIEM' logo and a navigation menu. The main content area is white and features a contact form. The form includes fields for 'Your Name (required)', 'Your Email (required)', 'Subject', and 'Your Message'. A 'SEND' button is located at the bottom of the form. To the right of the form, there are social media links for Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube, and a section titled 'REMEMBER TO FOLLOW US'. Below the form, there is a cartoon character wearing a headset and a speech bubble that says 'HELLO!'. The page also has a search bar in the top right corner and a 'Google Maps' link in the top left corner.

FIGURE 23: CONTACT SECTION

5 MEASURING RESULTS

STADIEM has indicated, among its KPIs, more than 1,500 visitors per year. In order to monitor the progress towards this result, visits to the website are measured and evaluated by using statistics measured by Google Analytics (GA). GA is the best tool for personalized views and graphs about type of users, geographical location, web referrals, most popular content, etc.

Analytics work by tracking 'tags', which are a small piece of JavaScript code that are installed on every page of the website to work properly. This data is then collected and shown in a 'report' page in the Google Analytics' admin interface.

What Google Analytics tracks, in detail:

- Visits: The total number of visits, including both new and returning visitors. A returning visitor would be counted twice or more in this number, and so 'visits' is a different measurement to 'absolute unique visits'.
- Page Views: The total number of pages viewed.
- Bounce Rate: The percentage of visitors who leave the site without viewing a second page (i.e. they click the 'back' button, type a new URL, close the window or session time-out - Usually 30 minutes). A good bounce rate is below 20%, 30% is standard, and anywhere over 50% would suggest a close look is needed to see why so many people are leaving the site on first glance.
- % New Visits: The percentage of visitors who were new; the difference between this and 100% is the percentage of returning visitors.

Also, Google Analytics includes an overview of where in the world the visitors are located, which languages they use, as well as a breakdown of the browsers and platforms they are using.

In summary, Google Analytics is the perfect tool to accurately measure the performance of the website. As such, web strategy should be constantly evolving, tweaking both traffic strategy and conversion processes to optimize the site.

Other popular applications in this field will be used to include the KPIs in Social Media channels. The combination of all these tools will allow us to have a complete view of our progress, defining improvements in line with the analysis of complete reports.

The evolution of the indicators will be revised periodically and the main results of the communication actions will be reported in the annual deliverable on "Dissemination and Communication activities", including, for instance, the following indicators:

- Number of visitors to the website
- Number of followers in Social Media accounts
- Number of newsletter receptors
- Socio-demographic data studies of the website visitors
- Information requests
- Engagement indicators

This helps to quantify more precisely the results obtained and define the upcoming milestones which will improve the quality of the communication.

Deliverable D5.2 (Outreach and impact creation strategy and plan), which will follow the current document, with expected delivery in January 2021, will offer a first report on the results achieved since the website's inception.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

As mentioned in the previous sections, STADIEM's website will be continuously updated (especially in terms of news articles and events added, but also in terms of promotional materials produced).

WP5 will also alter the structure according to results and feedback received. (or other necessities) This will inform needed changes such as, adding further sections and sub-sections.

Furthermore, from February 1st 2021, the website will be further populated to promote the launch of the first open call.

